

Information and Communication Technologies Usage across Rice Cultivators using Regression Modeling Approach

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Abstract: The study evaluated the information and communication technologies (ICT) usage and factors shaping ICT usage across rice growing farmers in Uttar Pradesh state of India. The study relied on multi stage sampling and data was collected from rice cultivators using a structured questionnaire in multiple dialects. The study evaluated the impact of farmers' age, family size, education, land type and training on respective ICT usage across time of rice cultivation. This research observed that age, family size, land type and training reported significant influence. Further analysis of cross factor interaction revealed that considered socio-demographic aspects seem to interact significantly across time period of research. The relationship between social demographical aspects and rice farmers' ICT usage needs serious incorporation of foresight for production to sustain levels. Farmers need to be sensitized with regard to ICT usage that ICT adoption is beneficial for meeting global levels and for enhancement of competitiveness and for yield realization.

Keywords: Regression modeling, Rice cultivators, ICT usage, Age, Uttar Pradesh

1. Introduction

Rice cultivation and ICT usage (Okeke et al., 2020) bears a reported history of mutual progress and productivity enhancement. The ICT usage across rice cultivators worldwide is on the rise on account of the positive synergies that reflect in agricultural marketing, agricultural productivity based gains and the realization of benefits. The ICT usage (Yila and Azeez, 2018) has not only enabled better realization of price yet also enables knowledge dissemination (Bojang et al., 2020), exchange of ideas, exposure to global

marketing practices as well as better awareness about implications of climate change for rice production. ICT usage is much more than mere ownership or possession of 2G or 4G mobile telephone. The studies (Sangbaupaun, 2012) on subject matter devote considerable focus on meaningful and purposeful usage of ICT tools (Devkota and Phuyal, 2018) for agricultural productivity enhancement, agricultural marketing and efficient usage of factors of production (Adegbidi, et al, 2012). The recent discourse on ICT usage among the farmers, rural hinterlands and across cultivators has exhibited positive and constructive outcomes vis a vis the reach to market, better knowledge absorption across various stage of cropping and across yield management. Yet in a developing economy like India, the ICT usage has risen marginally across rice cultivators. A host of studies (Aulakh and Jaspreet, 2015) from International Food Policy Research Institute; point to the active incorporation of workable ICT ideas like green SIM, kisan call centre, mKisan, eKisan, eSagu; yet the general outlook across rice cultivators (Balasubramanian et al., 2009) is not that much attuned to accepting the change in way the knowledge regarding agricultural practices is created and leveraged. This research hence extends the exploration of factors that seem to determine the variations in ICT usage amongst the rice cultivators in Uttar Pradesh state and seek to develop insights across the contextual phenomenon.

The rationale before the research is to analyze the factors and their relationships that seem to shape the ICT usage across rice cultivators in rural areas. The rationale is to examine the factors that shape up the rural ICT usage in terms of social demographics and the aspects that are prevalent in day to day lives of the rice growers. The research is expected to be more than relevant as ICT usage and demand for agricultural produce are interrelated. As per study (Lokeshwari, 2015) by FAO, the ICT usage at farm level is yet to materialize in consistent terms and current ICT usage is marked by large inconsistencies and infrequent disruptions in harmonious usage patterns. The rural level penetration of internet solutions, smartphone penetration and consistent broadband availability are still an issue. The e-readiness index across rural agricultural bases is still reported to be incompatible with global rural ICT usage trends and patterns. Hence the study makes sense in exploring the impact of social demographic aspects like age, gender, education, land type and training as shaping the prospects for ICT usage and regular adaptation of ICT devices and gadgets. The research assumes these hypotheses for assessment of impact of age, training, education and land type on farmer's ICT usage:

H1: There is significant impact of age, training, education and land type on farmer's ICT usage

H2: There is considerable interaction across age and family size in shaping rice cultivator's ICT usage.

H3: There is considerable interaction across education and family size in shaping rice cultivator's ICT usage.

H4: There is considerable interaction across land type and training in shaping rice cultivator's ICT usage.

2. Literature Review

The ICT usage exhibits a long history of shaping the marketing practices, dynamics and agriculture marketing tactics. The reviewed research illustrates that ICT usage not only enhances access, visibility and reach but also dampens the restrained flow of market information and multiples the effect of marketing communication. A study (Patel and Shukla, 2014) on agriculture marketing foresees immense opportunities for ICT mediated services and knowledge sharing in agricultural marketing. Another research (Bankar, 2020) called for immense applications of movement of agriculture product from the farm to target consumer.

The increase in usage of data driven marketing applications; in actual movement of product (Dabbara et al., 2020) from place to production to actual place of consumption marks enormous advantages in terms of price determination and value creation. A study (Ngasa, 2020) on role of digital marketing in rural agriculture transformation revealed the prevalence of ICT tools and digital literacy in shaping the fortunes and as essential to overcome information asymmetries. A research (Ogbeide-Osaretin and Ebhote, 2020) attributed the usage of ICT applications in enhancing the market accessibility of small business enterprises in agriculture sector. The studies (Grewal and Dharwadkar, 2001) elaborate on a large number of prospective merits of usage of ICT tools and applications in agriculture marketing. Especially in context of developing economy like India, adequate research attention is missing.

The existing literature on farmer calls for farmer based 'market orientation' as essential to innovate and adopt changes in practices. Most of the scholarly studies Aulakh and Jaspreet (2015) seem to link with ICT adoption with farmer based capability to adapt and learn about new farming practices and agricultural knowledge dissemination. Especially in wake of climate change and global warming (Gopalakrishnan, 2005), ICT usage has been advocated as essential in coping with the challenge. The usage of ICT for agricultural 'information dissemination' and overcoming 'information asymmetries'; remain a matter of intense research and analysis across Asian agricultural economies. The relationship between access to information and development (Obayelu and Ogunlade, 2006) attributes a larger research attention across context of developing economies and low developing economies.

Bernard and Dulle (2014) reported the incidence of 'information' and 'communication' tools as shaping farmer's decision making capabilities. Another research harped on the need for development of farmer's market orientation (Crick, 2018) and adaptability to changing market conditions. The small scale farmer's usage of modern communication

methods and applications has been observed as shaping his attitude and outlook with intelligent decision making and realization more profit per a quintal of produce being cultivated. A research study (Gopalakrishnan, 2005) by leading organization underlined the need for rapid technology adoption in order to facilitate information flows (Sennuga et al., 2020) and distribution across the marginalized sections of society.

The ICT usage (Yila and Azeez, 2018) has not only enabled better realization of price yet also enables knowledge dissemination (Bojang et al., 2020), exchange of ideas, exposure to global marketing practices as well as better awareness about implications of climate change for rice production. The studies by UNESCO and UNDP highlight the role of information and communication technologies in fostering climate for balanced decision making (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2015), increase in quantum of agricultural knowledge being accessed and harnessed for productivity enhancement. Regional level agriculture capacity development (Dabbara et al., 2020), practices transformation (Pillai and Sivathanu, 2020) and agriculture marketing (Obayelu and Ogunlade, 2006) have always been observed as reliant on each other. Agricultural knowledge enhancement (Mansour et al., 2019) engagement across farmer level has been reported to lead to constructive and positive changes in thinking and sense making with regard to selling price decision making. The reported emerging usage of ICT tools and application (Dabbara et al., 2020) has led to revolutionary changes in farmer based margin realization across developing economies. The farmer based incorporation of ICT as tool seems to overcome the limitations of traditional knowledge sharing means and methods and seems to facilitate real time information flow across major stakeholders. The lack of studies across rice cultivators' call for research focus on the intricacies of the phenomenon that seem to drive the ICT thrust.

3. Research Approach

In order to gain better understanding of determinants of ICT usage across traditional rice cultivators, the research model was constructed on basis of contingency framework and theory of planned behavior. The social demographic aspects and rational intention to indulge in ICT usage was interpreted as involving the rice cultivator's perceptions. The data was collected from across rice cultivators and was analyzed with aid of SPSS software version release 24.0. The detailed questionnaire was developed with the help of the literature in the field of the Agricultural Marketing and Literature available with the Universities situated in Uttar Pradesh. The questionnaire was designed as per the objectives of the study to get the desired results. After, the finalization of the questionnaire, it was sent to the subject expert to evaluate and examine the outliers which

could arise from the questionnaire. Once, the questionnaire was finalized, the pilot survey was conducted to test the results. After, the pilot survey, the actual questionnaire was filled through primary collection method from the respondents of districts of Varanasi, Ambedkarnagar, Allahabad, Gonda, Agra, Meerut, Muzaffarnagar, Saharanpur, Jhansi, Banda, Chitrakut, Jalaun, Kanpur Dehat, Etawah, Kheri and Sitapur. The Cronbach alpha of the pilot sample size was observed to be 0.745 which was acceptable for the primary data. Cronbach's alpha is an index of reliability associated with the variation accounted for by the true score of the underlying construct. The research collected the data from filed employed rice cultivators and deployed the SPSS as a statistical tool to refine and validate the data.

4. Regression Modeling

4.1. Regression equation involving farmer’s ‘age’, ‘family size’ , ‘education’, ‘land type’ and ‘training’

The linear regression was calculated to predict ‘ICT Usage’ based on farmer’s ‘age’, ‘family size’, ‘education’, ‘land type’ and ‘training’. The significant regression equation was observed [F(ICT USAGE)= ‘age’, ‘family size’, ‘education’ ‘land type’ and ‘training’] with an observed R of 0.872 as is shown in Table 1. The reported observations point towards the degree of freedom as 1 and equation was found [F(1(degree of freedom) = 23.878(F), p<0.000), with an R of 0.872. The respondents predicted the weight as equal to 1.285 + 0.120 (AGE) + 0.369 (FAMILY SIZE) + 0.265(EDUCATION) + 0.791 (LAND TYPE)+ 0.044 (TRAINING). The R (multiple correlation coefficient) is regarded as a measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable (farmer’s ICT adoption in this case). The reported value of 0.872 is a satisfactory measure of the multiple correlations. The R² represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variable as reported by the constituent independent variables. The observed R² of 0.761 depicts the 76.1 per cent variance in dependent on account of independent variables. Coefficients are given in Table 2.

$$ICT\ USAGE = 1.285 + 0.120 (AGE) + 0.369 (FAMILY\ SIZE) + 0.265(EDUCATION) + 0.791 (LAND\ TYPE) + 0.044 (TRAINING)$$

Table 1:Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.872 ^a	.761	.757	.36585

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), TRAINING, EDUCATION, FAMILYSIZE, LANDTYPE, AGE.

Table 2: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.285	.139		9.264	.000
	AGE	.120	.025	.206	4.720	.000
	FAMILYSIZE	.369	.034	.414	10.971	.000
	EDUCATION	.265	.041	.228	6.445	.000
	LANDTYPE	.791	.037	.719	21.198	.000
	TRAINING	.044	.034	.038	1.298	.195

Note: a. Dependent Variable: ICTUSAGE.

$$\text{MODEL I: ICT USAGE} = 1.285 + 0.120 (\text{AGE}) + 0.369 (\text{FAMILY SIZE}) + 0.265(\text{EDUCATION}) + 0.791 (\text{LAND TYPE}) + 0.044(\text{TRAINING})$$

4.2. Age and family size interaction

In similar prospect in order to ascertain the age and family size interaction as influencing the ICT usage as dependent variable, the two way ANOVA was applied. The result as exhibited in table 3 point to the statistically significant interaction across age and family size as independent variables. This is tantamount to observing that rice cultivator’s age based differences and family size based variations do considerably effect the farmer’s adoption of ICT usage in day to day agricultural activities involving rice cultivation.

Table 3: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Dependent Variable: ICTUSAGE)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	144.559 ^a	7	20.651	466.462	.000
Intercept	705.744	1	705.744	15940.983	.000
AGE	35.587	4	8.897	200.958	.000
FAMILYSIZE	6.556	2	3.278	74.046	.000
AGE * FAMILYSIZE	13.689	1	13.689	309.206	.000
Error	12.308	278	.044		
Total	1038.000	286			
Corrected Total	156.867	285			

Note: a. R Squared = .922 (Adjusted R Squared = .920).

4.3. Education and family size interaction

In likewise manner, the independent variables education and family size were evaluated for cross interaction in shaping the ICT usage across rice cultivators. The two way ANOVA was applied to ascertain the education and family size interaction as influencing the ICT usage as dependent variable. The result as exhibited in table below point to the

statistically significant interaction across education and family size as independent variables. This is tantamount to observing that rice cultivator’s education based differences and family size based variations do considerably effect the farmer’s adoption of ICT usage in day to day agricultural activities involving rice cultivation. As evident in the SPSS outcome in table 4, the significance value is less than 0.05, hence the interaction is leading to significant impact on shaping ICT usage. This is tantamount to observing that interaction is exerting impact on rice cultivator’s ICT usage.

Table 4: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Dependent Variable: ICTUSAGE)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	112.632 ^a	7	16.090	101.120	.000
Intercept	129.178	1	129.178	811.827	.000
EDUCATION	3.143	2	1.571	9.876	.000
FAMILYSIZE	61.693	2	30.846	193.856	.000
EDUCATION * FAMILYSIZE	6.217	3	2.072	13.024	.000
Error	44.235	278	.159		
Total	1038.000	286			
Corrected Total	156.867	285			

Note: a. R Squared = .718 (Adjusted R Squared = .711).

Age and family size interaction revealed the incidence of statistical interference as exhibited by MANOVA. The Wilk’s lambda measure of 0.000 pointed to statistically significant interaction between rice farmer’s age and family size as interacting mutually to shape farmer’s ICT usage tendencies, patterns and inclinations. This is shown in Table 5

Table 5: Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypot-thesis df	Error df	Sig.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.992	17683.079 ^b	2	277	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.008	17683.079 ^b	2	277	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	127.676	17683.079 ^b	2	277	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	127.676	17683.079 ^b	2	277	.000
AGE	Pillai's Trace	1.282	124.114	8	556	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.057	219.552 ^b	8	554	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	10.486	361.783	8	552	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	9.889	687.303 ^c	4	278	.000
FAMILYSIZE	Pillai's Trace	.798	92.239	4	556	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.244	142.043 ^b	4	554	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	2.933	202.356	4	552	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	2.873	399.406 ^c	2	278	.000

Table 5 continued

AGE * FAMILYSIZE	Pillai's Trace	.813	600.248 ^b	2	277	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.187	600.248 ^b	2	277	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	4.334	600.248 ^b	2	277	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	4.334	600.248 ^b	2	277	.000

Note: a. Design: Intercept + AGE + FAMILYSIZE + AGE * FAMILYSIZE. b. Exact statistic and c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.

4.4. Interaction between land type and training

As evident in outcome in table 6, the significance value is greater than 0.05, hence the interaction is failing to lead to significant impact on shaping ICT usage. This is tantamount to observing that interaction is failing to exert any impact on rice cultivator’s ICT usage.

Table 6: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	85.912 ^a	8	10.739	41.924	.000
Intercept	506.606	1	506.606	1977.729	.000
LANDTYPE	50.235	2	25.117	98.055	.000
TRAINING	.177	2	.088	.345	.709
LANDTYPE * TRAINING	.176	4	.044	.172	.953
Error	70.955	277	.256		
Total	1038.000	286			
Corrected Total	156.867	285			

Note: Dependent Variable: ICTUSAGE. R Squared = .548 (Adjusted R Squared = .535).

In simpler terms the ICT usage is not affected by rice cultivator’s land type and the training that the farmer has received. The model as depicted above and supporting hypothesis as mentioned in table 7, provided concise and clear cut evidence for age, training, education and land type as shaping rice cultivating farmer’s ICT usage. The interaction across considered variables further reflected on possible interactions as influencing ICT usage consistency.

Table 7: Summarizing the hypothesis statement

H	Hypothesis statement	Outcomes
H1	There is significant impact of age, training, education and land type on farmer’s ICT usage	Supported
H2	There is considerable interaction across age and family size in shaping rice cultivator’s ICT usage.	Supported
H3	There is considerable interaction across education and family size in shaping rice cultivator’s ICT usage.	Supported
H4	There is considerable interaction across land type and training in shaping rice cultivator’s ICT usage.	Not Supported

5. Conclusions and Implications

Rice cultivation and ICT usage need close coordination and possess meaningful lessons for policy makers, stakeholders, farmers, agricultural marketing value chain members as well as for farmer's price realization. ICT usage no doubt is crucial for access to global markets, for adoption of efficient agricultural and marketing practices; yet farmer's awareness and usage patterns are dismal. The relationship between social demographical aspects and rice farmer's ICT usage needs serious incorporation of foresight for production to sustain levels. Farmers need to be sensitized with regard to ICT usage that ICT adoption is beneficial for meeting global levels and for enhancement of competitiveness and for yield realization. For telecom operators this presents a unique opportunity to establish markets across rural hinterlands with product and service innovation. The research outcomes possess meaningful insights for agricultural value chain partners as well. The real time dissemination of agricultural information, climate change information, emerging trends with regard to soil fertility, varieties and crop self-life enhancement could entail benefits of updating with market trends and foster market orientation. The research implications are critical in the sense that they reflect significantly on the cross variable (age, training, education, family size) linkages as potentially shaping rice cultivator's ICT usage. ICT usage promotion is equally vital for rural community resilience and embedment into mainstream growth options. Amidst the background of ongoing epidemic breakout and climate change discourses, ICT usage promotion is more desired than ever before. Information needs of rice cultivators in Uttar Pradesh need to be met.

Rice cultivating farmers and ICT usage will remain a matter of extensive research attention. The technological and financial inclusion of rice cultivating farmers, their ICT adoption mindsets and consistency of ICT usage could be probable areas of future research. The cross regional, cross crop, cross climatic condition driven research can provide more insights into what is working and what is not working with regard to farmer's ICT usage promotion.

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